

RESULTS OF TREATMENT OF MALLORY-WEISS SYNDROME

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Relevance. Mallory-Weiss syndrome ranks first among non-ulcerative gastroduodenal bleeding. The disease is mainly found in representatives of the stronger sex aged 45-60 years, who consume excessive amounts of alcohol. To date, the main method of diagnosing Mallory-Weiss syndrome at the present stage is esophagogastroduodenoscopy, which is performed urgently and allows you to establish not only the etiology of bleeding, but also the nature [1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

The purpose of the study. To study the effectiveness of injectable hemostasis methods in Mallory-Weiss syndrome.

Materials and methods. The study included 28 patients who were hospitalized in the Khorezm branch of the Republican research centre of emergency medicine for Mallory-Weiss syndrome, in the period from 2015 to 2020.

Results. Based on these criteria, such as length, width and depth of rupture according to the clinical and anatomical features of Mallory-Weiss syndrome, it can be divided into the following 4 stages according to the classification of S.V. Timerbulatov.

To treat these patients, we used an endoscopic injection with 0.01% epinephrine solution.

Of all the patients, 96% (n=27) were male, and only 4% (n=1) belonged to the female sex.

The average age of men was 55-56 years, and the average age of women was 67-68 years.

Endoscopic injections were performed within 3 hours after hospitalization. All patients were hospitalized in the intensive care unit to prepare the upper digestive tract for endoscopic manipulations.

Injectable hemostasis with 0.01% epinephrine solution was used. There were 28 patients in this group with different stages of Mallory-Weiss syndrome. Effective treatment using this method was observed only in 9 (32%) patients, 7 of whom were patients with stage I Mallory-Weiss syndrome, and the remaining 2 patients with stage II. Only 2 patients with stage II Mallory-Weiss syndrome

managed to achieve complete hemostasis, while the rest experienced repeated bleeding. And in patients with stage III and IV, this method was absolutely ineffective.

Conclusions. Injectable hemostasis with 0.01% epinephrine solution gives the best result, in patients with stage I of Mallory -Weiss syndrome and menne is effective with stage II. In patients with stage III and IV, this method was absolutely ineffective.

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